

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF IMPACTS ON HELICOPTER BLADES USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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1 Introduction

During flight, helicopter blades may be subjected to impacts with various soft or hard bodies such as birds or hailstone. This work focuses on the experimental study of medium velocity (~70 m/s) impacts on helicopter blades.

A blade is composed of a main spar with unidirectional glass-epoxy, a skin and a rib made of hybrid glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy woven composite, a polyurethane foam core, and a protective stainless steel that covers the leading edge (Figure 1). Two types of impact can occur: a frontal impact on the leading edge and an oblique impact on the composite skin of the lower surface of the blade.

Fig. 1 : Description of the components of an helicopter blade

Many experimental studies concern impact on composite structures [1]. To carry these studies, post-mortem analyses are often performed, like C-Scan [2] or X-ray [3]. Sometimes high-speed camera coupled with full field measurement (with for instance Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [4] or Particule Image Velocimetry (PIV) [5]) are used to analyze the behavior of the target specimen.

The measurement of the velocity is a key issue, since it provides an estimate of the energy balance and the impact range. Most of the time, it is only measured just before impact with light gate timing

circuits. Another important issue is the evolution of the deceleration of the projectile during impact, used to estimate the impact force. Thus, an accelerometer is sometimes placed on the impactor, but its use is restricted to low velocity impacts carried out using drop weight devices [6]. Indeed, in the medium velocity impact range, the tests are performed with an air gun, and the projectile is a steel ball that can not be instrumented by accelerometers.

Image acquisition is usually performed with a high-speed camera, but most often for general visual assessments only. However, it is possible to analyze this sequence of images by computer vision algorithms. For instance, the Hough transform [7] is able to locate circles in an image. This is also the case of gradient based methods which may detect the contour of the projectile. Unfortunately, most of the time, it is limited to the measure of velocity because of the large measurement uncertainties [8]. Other methods taken from the motion analysis community are based on the tracking of markers. Since they have sub-pixels precision, they can provide velocity and acceleration with lower uncertainties. However, these methods are difficult to use in the context of impacts with air guns since the orientation of the projectile can not be mastered precisely.

In this work, the use of an optical measurement technique based on the motion analysis of the impactor within the sequence of images of a high speed digital camera is investigated. A new motion analysis technique is proposed for the tracking of a spherical object based on digital image correlation for the estimation of trajectory, velocity, acceleration and impact force during high velocity impacts. The originality is that the interpolation of the displacement is not only made of two rigid body

translations [9], but also of three rigid body rotations.

The paper is organized as follows. The digital image correlation method is explained in Section 2. The method is then illustrated in Section 3 on two impact tests: an oblique impact on a steel plate and a frontal impact on a cylindrical aluminium bar. Velocity and impact force measurements are compared to the results of numerical models. Then, the force values provided by this new measuring technique are used to study impacts on helicopter blades. Finally some concluding remarks are provided in section 4.

2 A new method to measure impact forces

2.1 Digital Image Correlation

Here, an enhanced measuring method is presented. The proposed method is based on the correlation of 2D monovision digital images [10].

Consider a pair of images f and g taken respectively at times t and $t+\Delta t$. During the time interval Δt , the projectile is assumed to undergo rigid body translations and rotations. The corresponding displacement u results in a variation of gray levels, such that the gray level conservation assumption is satisfied:

$$f(x) = g(x + u(x)) \quad (1)$$

where x is the position in the image.

A spline extrapolation of the gray level between pixels is used in order to measure a non-integer displacement [11].

Classically, the gray level conservation is written in a least square sense [12]. Find $u(x)$ minimizing the quadratic distance Φ^2 :

$$\Phi^2 = \int [f(x) - g(x + u(x))]^2 dx \quad (2)$$

This nonlinear problem is solved using an iterative process. At iteration k , an approximation of the displacement at the previous iteration $u_{k-1}(x)$ is assumed to be known. The problem consists in correcting this approximation: $u_k(x) = u_{k-1}(x) + \delta u(x)$. The correction $\delta u(x)$ is assumed to be small enough to allow for a first order Taylor expansion which results in the linearization of the problem:

$$\Phi^2 = \int [(f - g_u) - \delta u^T \nabla f]^2 dx \quad (3)$$

where $g_u(x) = g(x + u_{k-1}(x))$, $(f - g_u)$ being the discrepancy map. The space of unknown displacement δu being infinite, an approximation subspace is introduced:

$$\delta u(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n(x) q_n \quad (4)$$

where $\varphi_n(x)$ are the interpolation basis functions, q_n the corresponding degree of freedom (dof) and N the dimension of the approximation subspace. The use of such an interpolation leads to the resolution of the following linear system at iteration k :

$$Mq^k = b^k \quad (5)$$

where q^k is the degrees of freedom vector collecting the values q_n , and where the operator M and right hand side b^k of (5) read:

$$M_{ij} = \int \varphi_i(x)^T \nabla f \nabla f^T \varphi_j(x) dx \quad (6)$$

$$b_i^k = \int \varphi_i(x)^T \nabla f (f(x) - g(x + u_k(x))) dx$$

2.2 Interpolation

Many choices for the interpolation functions $\varphi_n(x)$ can be done.

In the literature, most frequently, these functions have a local support, and represent a set of piecewise constant or piecewise polynomial functions [10].

More recently, some global DIC methods have been proposed. They rely on global continuous basis functions, like for instance Fourier series [13], B-Splines [14].

The extended finite element method (X-FEM) was also used for digital image correlation in the presence of discontinuities [15]. A formulation based on the Proper Generalized Decomposition (PGD) has also been proposed recently [16]. When one has *a priori* relevant mechanical information, analytical [12] or numerical [17] basis function can be also used.

In this study, the projectile is a steel ball and is assumed to undergo rigid body translations and rotations between two images. Since the motion is captured by a single camera, the full 3D displacement can not be recovered. In particular, the translation along the z-axis (out-of-plane vector of the image plane) is assumed to be negligible. The displacement interpolation can first be based on the two in-plane translations only, as it is done with classical DIC techniques. Furthermore, in this study, the use of the three additional rotations functions is proposed, in order to encompass possible rotations of the projectile, as shown Fig.1.

Fig.1. Five rigid body translations and rotations used as a displacement basis for the ball. From left to right: x-axis translation, y-axis translation, y-axis rotation, x-axis rotation and z-axis rotation.

More precisely, as the displacement is assumed to be small between two images, the orthogonal projections of linearized rotations are used as basis functions. The modes are only defined within a circular region of interest (ROI) of radius R (the radius of the ball in pixels) centered on the ball center $C(x_c, y_c)$. Thus, the 5 basis functions are defined as follows:

$$\forall (x, y) \text{ such that } (x - x_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2 < R^2 :$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1(x, y) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}; & \varphi_2(x, y) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}; \\ \varphi_3(x, y) &= \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{1 - \frac{(x - x_c)^2}{R^2 - (y - y_c)^2}} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}; \\ \varphi_4(x, y) &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \sqrt{1 - \frac{(y - y_c)^2}{R^2 - (x - x_c)^2}} \end{pmatrix}; \\ \varphi_5(x, y) &= \begin{pmatrix} y_c - y \\ x - x_c \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

2.3 Measurement over time

The high speed digital camera provides a sequence of N_i images $\{f_i\}_{0 \leq i \leq N_i}$. The procedure described above is used to measure the displacement of the

ball between two consecutive images, namely with $f=f_i$ and $g=f_{i+1}$. Thus, the measured quantity is a displacement increment, which corresponds to the velocity, when divided by the time lapse between two images.

In [4] it is preferred to measure the displacement between image f_0 and image f_i , in order to minimize measurement uncertainties on the displacement field, which is the quantity of interest of the analysis. In the work described herein, the quantities of interest are velocity and acceleration. It is thus preferred to measure the velocity field in order to minimize the amplification of noise by differentiation with respect to time. In addition, the fact that the lighting conditions (reflection, overall brightness...) change significantly from the beginning to the end of the sequence, the fact that sometimes the paint is peeling because of the shock and the fact that sometimes the deformation of the target masks a part of the projectile, are arguments that reinforce this choice.

3 Application to impacts on helicopter blades

3.1 Validation of the DIC measuring technique

Two kinds of impact tests, an oblique and a frontal impact test, have been carried out with a gas gun. To validate the measures, these tests are performed on two metallic specimens and the results are compared to Finite Element calculations.

For the oblique impact test, the target is a steel plate of dimensions 200x400x1mm. The angle between the firing axis and the specimen is 15° . The right and left edges of the specimen are simply supported (Fig 2.a). For that test, the steel ball (19mm diameter and 28g weight) is propelled at an average initial velocity of 80 m/s (~ 90 J). For the frontal test, the target is a cylindrical bar made of aluminium alloy (300mm long and 18mm diameter). The specimen is positioned perpendicular to the firing axis (Fig 2.b). For this test, the steel ball (30mm diameter and 110g weight) is propelled at an average initial velocity of 70 m/s (~ 270 J).

Fig 2 : Setup of the impact tests – (a) oblique impact on an inclined steel plate monitored by side view and (b) frontal impact of aluminium cylindrical bar monitored by a top view.

For both tests, the impactor is a hardened steel ball entirely covered by a black and white painted speckle. Sequences of images were acquired by a Photron APX-RS CMOS high speed digital camera. Images were obtained at two different rate/resolution compromises: 20000fps (512x512 px resolution) and 36000fps (512x128 px resolution) for the oblique and frontal impacts respectively. The shutter speed was set to 1/81000s in order to limit the motion blur to less than 4 pixels wide and reduce uncertainties. Three Dedolight spots were used to provide enough light to keep an acceptable contrast.

An example of the analyzed image is presented in Fig 3 for an oblique impact. The circular ROI automatically adapted is plotted (yellow circle). The measured positions of the center of the ball throughout the image sequence are reported by yellow + symbols on the image. On this figure, one can see that a part of the ball is hidden by the plate specimen because of its deflection. However, the adopted technique seems robust in this respect.

Fig 3 : Measured positions (+) and position of the ball (circle) at $t=0.65\text{ms}$ during the contact with the specimen.

More, the digital images and the measured position of the ball are plotted in Fig 4 before, during and after a frontal impact. The positions estimated with an without taking into consideration the rotation of the impactor (denoted respectively r_{bt+rot} and r_{bt}) are plotted. The ball undergoes a slight rotation that the r_{bt} algorithm does not manage. Indeed, in Fig 4.c, the displacement (and thus the velocity) is underestimated when only rigid body translations are used as displacement interpolation. In opposition, it seems that the position is much more accurate with the enhanced interpolation basis. This results in a better estimation of the after-impact kinetic energy. Furthermore, the update of the position of the ROI is more accurate. In practice, one can sometimes observe that the r_{bt} algorithm loses the impactor due to the fact that the error accumulates. This is not the case with the r_{bt+rot} algorithm.

Fig 4 : Positions of the ball retrieved by the DIC technique based on rigid translation only (solid line) and with the addition of rotations (dashed line) before impact at $t=0.639\text{ms}$ (a), during the first contact $t=1.4167\text{ms}$ (b) and after impact at $t=3.56\text{ms}$ (c).

In order to validate the measuring method, the two impact tests have been modeled. These finite element explicit simulations are carried out with the commercial software Radioss. The impactor was modeled using a Radioss spherical rigid wall, which is an undeformable solid. Johnson-Cook model was chosen for the material behavior of the steel plate and the aluminium bar. When the stress σ in the material reaches the yield stress a , the constitutive law becomes:

$$\sigma = (a + b \cdot \epsilon_p^n) \left(1 + c \cdot \ln \frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0} \right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{T - T_i}{T_{melt} - T_i} \right)^m \right) \quad (8)$$

where b is the hardening stiffness, ϵ_p the plastic strain, n an hardening parameter, c the strain rate coefficient, $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ the reference strain rate, T the temperature, T_i the initial temperature, T_{melt} the melting temperature and m a temperature parameter. The material characteristics are given in Table 1.

Steel			Aluminium				
E (MPa)	190000	n	0.7	E (MPa)	60400	n	0.37
ν	0.25	c	0.12	ν	0.33	c	0.1
a (MPa)	400	$\dot{\epsilon}_0$	0.2	a (MPa)	175	$\dot{\epsilon}_0$	0.18
b (MPa)	750	m	0	b (MPa)	223	m	0

Table 1 : Material characteristics for the Johnson–Cook model chosen to represent the material behavior of the steel plate and the aluminium bar.

For the oblique impact simulation, the plate was modeled using standard shell elements with hourglass stabilization. The mesh size is smaller in the impacted area (Fig 5.a). The edge length varies from 0.5mm to 10mm. For the frontal impact simulation, the bar was modeled using standard 8-node three-dimensional elements with full integration. The mesh size is lower in the impacted region (Fig 5.b). The edge length varies from 1mm to 15mm.

Fig 5: Modeling of the impact tests: (a) oblique impact (b) frontal impact.

The evolution of the velocity and impact force for the oblique impacts are plotted in Fig 6. The calculated velocity and reaction load well correlates the measured forces.

Fig 6 : Comparison of the simulated and measured x and y components of the velocity and impact force corresponding to an oblique impact on a steel plate. In green, the simulation and in black the measurement with only rigid body translations (solid line) and translations + rotations (dashed line).

The measured impact force and velocity of the impactor during the frontal impact on the aluminium bar are reported in Fig 7. If the shape of the velocity of the simulation and the measurement are similar, there is a mismatch on its final amplitude. One reason of such a difference could be the fact that damping is neglected in the modeling. Nevertheless, according to the impact force, the match between the simulation and the measurement is very good. Indeed, one can observe the same number of peaks. The measured position and amplitude also well correlates the calculation results.

Fig 7 : Comparison of the simulated and measured x component of the velocity and impact force corresponding to a frontal impact on an aluminium bar. In green, the simulation and in black the measurement with only rigid body translations (solid line) and translations + rotations (dashed line).

3.2 Application to the study of oblique impacts

The purpose of these tests is to study the influence of the material of the skin on the response of composite sandwich panels subjected to oblique impacts.

The specimens are composite sandwich panels with a polymeric foam core. The first tested skin is made up of two plies of glass/epoxy woven fabric oriented at 0–90° from the firing direction. The second tested skin is made up of two plies of carbon/epoxy woven fabric oriented at 0–90° from the firing direction. The fabrics characteristics are given Table 2.

glass / epoxy		carbon / epoxy	
Density (kg/m ³)	1900	Density (kg/m ³)	1530
Elastic modulus (Mpa)	19400	Elastic modulus (Mpa)	54000
Shear modulus (Mpa)	3000	Shear modulus (Mpa)	4500
Poisson ratio	0,13	Poisson ratio	0,045
Tensile strength (Mpa)	400	Tensile strength (Mpa)	800

Table 2 : Mechanical characteristics of the glass/epoxy woven fabric and the carbon/epoxy woven fabric

The projectile is a steel ball with a diameter of 19 mm and a mass of 28 g. The impact angle is set to 15° from the firing axis. The impact velocity is 70m/s.

Fig 8 shows the velocity of the impactor and the impact force measured with the presented DIC method.

Fig 8 : Impactor velocity versus time for a glass/epoxy skin (orange line) and a carbon/epoxy skin (black line)

The velocity of the projectile after impact is lower for the specimen with the carbon/epoxy skin than for the specimen with the glass/epoxy skin. A balance of the kinetic energy of the ball before and after impact shows that the carbon fiber skin has absorbed 30.52 J and the glass fiber skin 10.73 J.

Fig 9 : Normal impact load versus normal displacement for a glass/epoxy skin (orange line) and a carbon/epoxy skin (black line)

Indeed, the analysis of the evolution of the normal impact load (Fig 9) shows that the failure of the facesheet occurs for a load 26% lower for the carbon/epoxy skin. Consequently, the carbon fiber skin is more damaged than the glass fiber skin. That is why the dissipated energy is higher for the woven carbon/epoxy skin.

4. Conclusion

A Digital Image Correlation method was used to analyze the image sequence of medium velocity impacts carried out by air guns. It was shown that the method provides reliable estimation of the evolution of velocity and impact force during the impact. Indeed, the comparison with reliable numerical simulation reveals a good match between measured and simulated fields. This method is then proposed to analyze oblique impact tests on composite sandwich structures made with different composite facesheets.

The major contribution of this work is a new accurate method for the experimental measurement of impact velocities and impact forces during gas gun impact tests. To go further, the method could be extended to stereo correlation, in order to avoid the assumption of planarity of the trajectory of the impactor. Another expectation of stereo correlation is that the double amount of informations could be used as regularization.

References

- [1] S. Abrate. “*Impact on composite structures*”. Cambridge University Press, 1998
- [2] C. Bouvet, B. Castanié, M. Bizeul, J. Barrau. “*Low velocity impact modelling in laminate composite panels with discrete interface elements*” *International Journal Solids Structures* 46 (2009) 2809–2821.
- [3] F. Aymerich, F. Dore, P. Priolo, “*Prediction of impact-induced delamination in cross-ply composite laminates using cohesive interface elements*” *Composite Science and Technology* 68 (2007) 2383–2390.
- [4] G. Besnard, F. Hild, J.-M. Lagrange, P. Martinuzzi, S. Roux, “*Analysis of necking in high speed experiments by stereocorrelation*”, *Int J of Impact Engineering* 49 (2012) 179–191.
- [5] J. Borg, M. Morrissey, C. Perich, T. Vogler, L. Chabildas, “*In situ velocity and stress characterization of a projectile penetrating a sand target: Experimental measurements and continuum simulations*”, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 51 (2013) 23–35.
- [6] B. Castanié, C. Bouvet, Y. Aminanda, J.-J. Barrau, P. Thevenet, “*Modelling of low energy/low velocity impact on nomex honeycomb sandwich structures with metallic skins*”, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 35 (2008) 620–634.
- [7] P. Hough, “*Machine analysis of bubble chamber pictures*”, in: *Int. Conf. High Energy Accelerators and Instrumentation*.
- [8] H. Abdulhamid, A. Kolopp, C. Bouvet, S. Rivallant, “*Experimental and numerical study of AA5086-H111 aluminum plates subjected to impact*”, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 51 (2013) 1–12.
- [9] B.D. Lucas and T. Kanade. “*An iterative image registration technique with an application to stereo vision*”. In *Proceedings of Imaging Understanding Workshop*, pages 121–130, 1981
- [10] M.A. Sutton, W.J. Wolters, W.H. Peters, W.F. Ranson, and S.R. McNeill. “*Determination of displacements using an improved digital correlation method*”. *Image and Vision Computing*, 1(3):133–139, 1983
- [11] H. Schreier, J. Braasch, M. Sutton, “*Systematic errors in digital image correlation caused by intensity interpolation*”. *Optical Engineering* 39 (2000) 2915–2921.
- [12] S. Roux, F. Hild, “*Stress intensity factor measurements from digital image correlation: post-processing and integrated approaches*”, *Int J. Fract* 140 (2006) 141–157.
- [13] S. Roux, F. Hild, Y. Berthaud, “*Correlation image velocimetry : a spectral approach*”, *Applied Optics* 41 (2002).
- [14] P. Cheng, M. Sutton, H. Schreier, S. R. McNeill, “*Full-field speckle pattern image correlation with b-spline deformation function*”, *Experimental mechanics* 42 (2002) 344–352.
- [15] J. Réthoré, S. Roux, F. Hild, “*An extended and integrated digital image correlation technique applied to the analysis of fractured samples*”, *Eur J. Comput Mech* 18 (2009) 285–306.
- [16] J.-C. Passieux, J.-N. Périé, “*High resolution digital image correlation using proper generalized decomposition: PGD-DIC*”, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 92 (2012) 531–550.
- [17] H. Leclerc, J.-N. Périé, S. Roux, F. Hild, “*Integrated digital image correlation for the identification of mechanical properties*”, in: *Gagalowicz A, Philips W (eds) MIRAGE*, volume 5496, pp. 161–171.